

ON CHLORALAMIDES. CHLORAL-5-ACETAMIDO-SALICYLAMIDE AND RELATED COMPOUNDS.

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5-Acetamidosalicylamide has been condensed with chloral to yield the usual product of the type $R'CO \cdot NH \cdot CH(OH) \cdot CCl_2$. The acetamido group, unlike the negative groups, in the position 5 does not inhibit the condensation.

Chloral-5-acetamidosalicylamide gives with dimethyl sulphate, benzoyl chloride and acetic anhydride, the related derivatives; and, on dehydration, 6-acetamidobenzo-2-trichloromethylmetoxazone.

5-Aminosalicylamide does not condense with chloral to give a simple aldol type condensation product, $R'CO \cdot NH \cdot CH(OH) \cdot CCl_2$, due to the complication brought about by the highly active amino group (*cf.* Wallach, *Ber.*, 1871, 4, 668; Hirwe and Kulkarni, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 13A 49). However, 5-acetamidosalicylamide easily condenses on heating with a moderate excess of chloral to yield quantitatively chloral-5-acetamidosalicylamide (I).

The condensation product (I) retains the phenolic group and decomposes at its melting point into the amide and chloral. But as the substituent $\text{-NH} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_3$ in the position 5 is not much of a negative nature, the chloral-amide unlike chloral-5-chlorosalicylamide (Hirwe and Rana, *Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1346) is sufficiently stable in every respect.

Thus, it is observed that the formation, as also the stability, of the variously 5-substituted chloralsalicylamides depends on the nature of the substituents; the negative substituents in the position 5 inhibit the condensation (Hirwe and Rana, *loc. cit.*; Hirwe, Gavankar and Patil, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1940, 11A, 512), but it is promoted as the substituents tend to become positive.

Hirwe and Wagh (*private communication*) attempted to condense 3-acetamidosalicylamide with chloral, but obtained no definite product. This result is interesting and indicates that although the negative substituents

in the position 3 promote the condensation, the tendency deteriorates as the substituents become positive.

On dehydration with cold, concentrated sulphuric acid, chloral-5-acetamidosalicylamide (I) gives 6-acetamidobenzo-2-trichloromethylmetoxazone (II); insolubility in alkalis and absence of colouration with ferric chloride support the ring formation. The latter does not hydrolyse with ammonia to yield the corresponding α -amino compound, like 6:8-dichlorobenzo-2-trichloromethylmetoxazone (Hirwe and Rana, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1939, 8, iii, 243); hot alcoholic ammonia decomposes it in an unrestrained fashion. It gives a monoacetyl derivative, but no hydrochloride.

The compound (I) gives with dimethyl sulphate and benzoyl chloride the corresponding derivatives; but, when heated with acetic anhydride and two drops of concentrated sulphuric acid, it yields 6-acetamidobenzo-2-trichloromethylmetoxazone (II) and its acetyl derivative, instead of the usual diacetyl derivative which, however, is obtained when the chloralamide is treated with acetic anhydride at 0° in 10% sodium hydroxide solution. This procedure generally helping the formation of either an α -anhydro derivative, or a benzometoxazone (Hirwe and Rana, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1938, 7, iii, 174; 1939, 8, iii, 243).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of 5-Acetamidosalicylamide with Chloral: Chloral-5-acetamidosalicylamide.—A mixture of powdered 5-acetamidosalicylamide (5 g.) and chloral (15 c.c.) in a boiling tube, fitted with an air condenser, was gently heated on a wire gauze, until the clear solution suddenly solidified. It was kept at the room temperature overnight and then poured into ice-water, triturated, filtered off, washed and dried. The compound, soluble readily in methanol, alcohol, glacial acetic acid and acetone, sparingly in chloroform, benzene, and difficultly in hot water and ether, crystallised from alcohol in colourless, shining prisms, m.p. $176-77^\circ$ (decomp.), yield 6 g. It gave a violet colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 39.00; H, 3.27; N, 8.23; Cl, 31.01. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_2Cl_3$ requires C, 38.66; H, 3.25; N, 8.21; Cl, 31.16 per cent.)

Dehydration of Chloral-5-acetamidosalicylamide with Concentrated Sulphuric Acid: 6-Acetamidobenzo-2-trichloromethylmetoxazone.—Powdered chloral-5-acetamidosalicylamide (5 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) in the cold, and the solution kept inside a desiccator for 24 hours. When it was poured on to crushed ice, a white solid separated which was filtered off, washed and dried. The solid, soluble in methanol, alcohol, acetone, glacial acetic acid and benzene, crystallised

from alcohol in white, shining plates, m.p. 218-19°, yield 4 g. It gave no colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 41.18; H, 2.96; N, 8.95; Cl, 32.94. $C_{11}H_9O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires C, 40.81; H, 2.81; N, 8.66; Cl, 32.90 per cent).

The *acetyl derivative*, prepared from the above compound (1 g.), acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (2 drops), crystallised from alcohol in white, fine needles, m.p. 197-98°. It gave no colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 47.10. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 29.12 per cent).

Methoxychloral-5-acetamido-2-methoxybenzamide.—To a solution of chloral-5-acetamidosalicylamide (2 g.) in sodium hydroxide (20 c.c., 10% solution) at 0° was added dimethyl sulphate (2 g.) with constant shaking. The mixture was kept overnight in a refrigerator, when a paste separated, which solidified on long standing with water. The solid, soluble in methanol, alcohol, acetone and glacial acetic acid, crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 166-67°. It gave no colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: Cl, 29.01. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 28.82 per cent).

α-Benzoyloxychloral-5-acetamido-2-benzoyloxybenzamide.—Chloral-5-acetamidosalicylamide (2 g.), when treated as above with benzoyl chloride (2 g.), gave a paste which solidified on triturating with dilute sodium carbonate solution and on standing with water in a refrigerator for a long time. The solid, soluble in methanol, alcohol, acetone and benzene, separated from methanol as a white powder; m.p. 187-88°. It gave no colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: Cl, 19.66. $C_{23}H_{19}O_6N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 19.36 per cent).

α-Acetoxychloral-5-acetamido-2-acetoxybenzamide.—Chloral-5-acetamidosalicylamide (2 g.), under a similar treatment as above, with acetic anhydride (2 g.) gave a solid which is soluble readily in alcohol, acetone, glacial acetic acid and sparingly in benzene. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 212-14°, and gave no colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: Cl, 24.93. $C_{17}H_{15}O_6N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 25.00 per cent).

6-Acetamidobenzotrichloromethylmetoxazone.—A mixture of chloral-5-acetamidosalicylamide (2 g.), acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (2 drops) was heated in a boiling tube fitted with an air condenser on a water-bath for 2 hours. The dark brown liquid that resulted was poured into boiling water, when a solid was obtained, soluble in methanol, alcohol, acetone, glacial acetic acid and benzene. It gave no colouration with ferric chloride and was found to be a mixture of the above benzometoxazone and its acetyl derivative. They were separated

by fractional crystallisation from alcohol in which the latter is less soluble and identified by taking mixed melting points with authentic specimens of the substances prepared above.

Methyl 5-acetamidosalicylate was prepared from methyl 5-amino-salicylate by the action of acetyl chloride in pyridine medium (Binhorn and Hollandt, *Annalen*, 1898. 301, 111). It separated as needles from alcohol, m.p. 147-48°.

5-Acetamidosalicylamide.—Methyl 5-acetamidosalicylate (20 g.) and liquor ammonia (200 c.c., d_4^{20} 0.888) were mixed together in a pressure bottle and mechanically shaken for 6 hours, when a dark solution was obtained. It was concentrated on a water-bath to obtain a solid which was triturated with dilute hydrochloric acid, filtered off, washed and dried. The solid, soluble in hot water, alcohol, acetone and glacial acetic acid, crystallised from hot water in colourless needles and from alcohol in square plates, m.p. 204.6°, yield 16.5 g. It was found to crystallise with one molecule of water which it lost at 110° falling into powder. It gave a violet colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 50.82; H, 5.64; N, 13.40; H₂O, 8.58. C₉H₁₀O₃N₂ · H₂O requires C, 50.94; H, 5.66; N, 13.21; H₂O, 8.49 per cent).

The late Prof. N. W. Hirwe was keenly interested in these investigations, and from him the author had received much valuable advice.

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